

A Scientist and Haiku Poet

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FLORIN VASILIU was born in Bucharest, Romania, in March 11, 1929. He is graduated as chemist engineer, and worked in production, design, research, in higher education and in the field of the products quality. He published eight technical books, among which the most important are: *Metode de analiză a calității produselor*, (Methods of analyses of products quality). Ceres Publishing House, Bucharest 1983, (with N. Vericiuc), *Controlul modern al calității produselor* (Modern control of products' quality), Ceres Publishing House, Bucharest 1985 first edition, and 1987 the second edition. He published 46 technical and scientific papers, in "Celuloză și Hârtie" (Pulp and Paper), "Revista de Chimie" (Chemical Magazine), "Calitatea Producției și Metrologie" (Production quality and Metrology) and "Calitatea" (Quality) magazines. Also, he presented scientific works and papers at International Conferences and Symposiums: Conference "STAQUAREL 80" from Prague, The Seventh Conference on Probability Theory, Brașov, Romania 1982, International Symposium on Cellulose Chemistry and Technology, Iași România 1989. He took part at Conference inter-academic exchanges: Sofia, Bulgaria 1975, Beijing, China 1983, Prague Tchechoslovakya 1984, Hanju and Pyongyang North Korea 1986, and technical and commercial contacts in Germany, Japan, Poland, Egypt, France, Italy, Bulgaria, Tchechoslovakya, China, Korea, Finland. At present he works as professor in The University PRO HUMANITAS, Bucharest, Romania.

The Academician Octav Onicescu wrote in the preface of the *Metode de analiză a calității produselor*, that Florin Vasiliu is situated "...among the passionate and disinterested carriers of this new form of human activity".

After his travels in Japan, China, Korea, Florin Vasiliu wrote three books about the culture, civilization and history of Japan: *Pe Meridianul Yamato*, (On The Meridian Yamato), Sport Turism Publishing House, Bucharest, 1982, *De la Pearl Harbor la Hiroshima*, (From Pearl Harbor to Hiroshima), Dacia Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca 1986, *Interferențe lirice – Constelația haiku*, (Lyrics interpretations – Haiku Constellation), Dacia Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca 1988, and in this last year he published *Umbra libelulei*, (The dragonfly's shade), Anthology of Romanian haiku, and *Tolba cu licurici* (The bag with glow worms), published by Haiku Publishing House, Bucharest.

He also published 28 literary papers and poetry in many literary magazines from Romanian and Japan, and he was honored with the Prize of "Poesis" magazine, in 1990 for poetry, studies, commentaries, and for "Haiku" Magazine". Florin Vasiliu is editor-in-chief of the HAIKU magazine for Romanian-Japanese interpenetrations. He publishes also a "Collection of the Haiku Magazine", in which appear with haiku poetry of Romanian poets.

Florin Vasiliu is President of Romanian Haiku Society, Vice president of Nipponica Society, member of the Writers' Union of Romania, member of the Haiku International Association (Japan), fellow of the Paradoxist Literary Movement Association (U.S.A.)

On the occasion of the visit in Romania at a meeting of the literary circle of Romanian Haiku Society in Bucharest, Mr. Sono Uchida, the President of Haiku International Association wrote: "The style of the meeting differs somewhat from such a gathering in Japan in that winning verses are not chosen. The participants had anonymously submitted a haiku on the theme of

source (...). Vasiliu read the verses out loud and the participants discussed then (...). The seriousness of purpose and enthusiasm of the gathering were most impressive (...). The economic situation in Romania is still extremely difficult (...). It seemed to me that the hardship they endured made Romanian haikins – haiku poets – even more serious about composing haiku” (“International Haiku”, in *The Daily Yomiuri*, Wednesday, July 28, 1993, p. 9).

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